

External State Spoilers In Peace Processes: Analysis Of India's Role In Afghanistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 27, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 30, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Hybrid Conflict, Pakistan, Spoilers, Spoiling Tactics, Terrorism.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7041801</p>	<p><i>In a hybrid conflict, parties that hinder path to peace processes for their desired goals and interests are termed as spoilers. Afghanistan represents a hybrid conflict, wherein internal and external spoilers sabotage peace processes for their vested interests. This study analyses different tactics that India uses as an external state spoiler to sabotage peace processes in Afghanistan which have implications for Pakistan. The study finds that India deployed several violent and non-violent spoiling tactics in Afghanistan. Non-violent tactics include non-recognition of parties to the conflict, building anti-Pakistan narrative, labelling, financing Afghan society against Pakistan, exploiting ethnic and religious differences and interference in guise of development projects through use of soft power strategy. The violent tactics include support to terrorist organizations and internal spoilers, use of Indian Embassy, consulates and its intelligence agency for clandestine operations to sabotage peace processes. Data for this study was collected through documents and semi-structured interviews and analyzed by a thematic approach.</i></p>

Introduction

Post-9/11 Afghanistan represents complex and complicated conflict which represents a hybrid warfare (Korybko, 2017) wherein internal and external spoilers seek to “hinder, delay or undermine conflict settlement” through violent and non-violent means and for various motives (Newman and Richmond, 2006). To settle Afghan conflict, a series of negotiations had been conducted including the Bonn Process (2001), 2009-2010 Peace Talks, 2012 Peace Dialogue and the Murree Peace Talks (2015) but these peace processes failed. The Doha Peace Talks (2013-2020) also took longer to find the solution to Afghan conflict.

Since Pakistan's inception, New Delhi played a negative role in Afghanistan utilizing Islamabad and Kabul differences to strategically encircle Pakistan thereby creating the threat of a two-front scenario for Islamabad (Kasuri, 2016). Post 9/11 era marked the continuous spoiling behaviour of India in the context of hybrid conflict in Afghanistan. India, geographically external to Afghan conflict, supported internal spoilers against Pakistan and employed spoiling tactics both violent and non-violent to disrupt and delay conflict settlement in a bid to destabilize Pakistan and pursue its hegemonic designs in the region. The spoiler tactics used by India as political or nonviolent measures included manipulating Afghan situation politically, divert attention, non-recognition of the parties to the conflict, specially Afghan Taliban and Haqqani group; labelling, media narrative and propaganda campaigns, delay and disruption of progress in peace processes by supporting the intrastate spoilers against Pakistan and even using Afghan government and U.S. support to create a wedge between Kabul and Afghan Taliban and thereby influencing the peace conflict settlement. The military means or violent tactics used by India include assassinations, sabotaging the conflict settlement by carrying out terror activities in Afghanistan and Pakistan in collaboration with Afghan National Directorate of Security (NDS) (Jaffery, 2020). The spoiling role of India has political, security and economic implications for Pakistan and the region.

Research Questions

1. Why India pursues spoiling behaviour and what spoiling tactics does India employ in Afghanistan?
2. What are the implications of India's spoiling behaviour for Pakistan?

Conceptual Framework

Grossman (1991) described the concept of spoiler by elaborating that the wars or excessive dragged-out conflicts give profitable chances for some parties to draw the money from the conflict. These parties act as spoilers. Stedman (1997) defines spoilers as “leaders and parties who believe that peace emerging from negotiations threaten their power, worldview, and interests, and use violence to undermine attempts to achieve it.” According to Stedman, internal and external spoilers exist in a conflict. Internal spoilers are those groups that have signed the agreement and want the continuity of negotiations. Their spoiling behaviour is to keep their interests protected and strengthen their position in the negotiations. Internal spoilers are sometimes motivated by another

party, the outside spoilers. This motivation leads to arousal of conflict and sabotaging the peace process, making the objectives of outside spoiler accomplished. Stedman notes that external spoilers inside the country of the conflict, who are excluded or exclude themselves from peace negotiations, they use violence or other tactics such as massacre or building of alliance among each camp or groups to derail any peace agreement. Their vested interests in the state drive their spoiling nature. Stern and Druckman (2000, pp. 178-183) point out that external or international peace makers who tend to have an efficient strategy to control and limit spoilers can lessen the damage, whereas if the former fails to do so, the victory of the spoiler is the result of high causality rate. Kydd and Walter (2002) maintain the success of the peace negotiations to be purely in the hands of outside party suggesting them to be the real spoilers in the peace processes. Aggestam (2006) defines spoilers as “leaders and factions who view a particular peace as opposed to their interests and who are willing to use violence to undermine it.” Newman and Richmond (2006) argue that external actors outside the country of the conflict could spoil the conflict settlement by helping domestic spoilers and their tactics. They signify the importance of external spoilers to be the main hurdle in ensuring peace. They maintain that groups which negatively affect the efforts are because they fear their rights and potentials to be under threat and not secured. Newman and Richmond argue that spoiling behavior does not finish or cancel a peace process but introduces new sets of interests which surely will lapse time to solve the issue. By slowing down or holding up the process, recognition or admittance political and legal formations all are the indirect sources which are under direct control of spoilers. Zahar (2010) describe the use of violence by external parties acting as spoilers paves the way for internal spoilers to use it.

External spoilers prove to be the backbone for some of internal spoilers. They drive their vested interests through the internal spoilers who too in fact achieve their own desired goals. In that sense, the internal spoilers are the puppets in the hands of external spoilers. To achieve their hidden agenda, the major tactic is the use of overt activities specifically killing of leaders and mass explosions and establishment of linkages with the forces and agencies to sabotage the peace processes.

The conceptual framework of this study is based on the arguments drawn from existing literature on spoilers, spoiling behaviour and tactics. This framework will be used to assess India’s role as an external state spoiler in the peace processes in Afghanistan.

Table 1: India as an External State Spoiler	
Political/Non-Violent Tactics	Military/Violent Tactics
Non-recognition of parties to the conflict	Sabotage peace process by supporting terrorist organizations
Attempts to stall the peace processes	Support to internal spoilers for continued strife in Afghanistan
Building anti-Pakistan narrative	Use of Indian Embassy/ Consulates for clandestine operations
Labelling	The RAW-NDS nexus to sabotage peace processes
Financing Afghan society against Pakistan	
Exploiting the ethnic and religious differences	
Soft Power as a spoiling tactic	

Research Methodology

The research is exploratory based on qualitative method. It employs the following data collection methods:

1. Scrutiny of Documents: Data was collected from journal articles, books, newspapers, speeches, online resources and live broadcasted interviews.
2. Interviews: Semi-structured interviews were conducted from Defence Minister of Pakistan, subject experts, defense and military analysts, academicians and eminent journalists for details and depth. The Defence Minister provided his response in written form. Responses from all other interviewees were audio recorded as notes. Questions regarding India’s spoiling behaviour, tactics deployed to sabotage peace talks and implications for Pakistan have been asked. The semi structured interviews allowed the interviewees the freedom to express their opinions with significant flexibility.

Data Analysis: The analysis of documents led to identify patterns and tactics of New Delhi’s spoiling behaviour and its implications for Islamabad. Deductive analysis was carried out to build categories in advance for the following themes:

- Indian Motives of spoiling behaviour in Afghanistan
- Indian spoiling tactics categorized into violent and nonviolent measures
- Implications for Pakistan

The research mapped connections in the data to the above-mentioned specific categories in the following way (“How to analyse,” 2022).

- The annotation of interview transcripts was done to label relevant words and phrases, for identifying important concepts and opinions.
- Categories and subcategories were created to align data with critical themes
- The data was segmented to connect the categories for analysis.
- The results were interpreted and written in light of spoiler’s theories and concepts relevant to the research study.

Results And Discussion

India’s Motives Behind the Spoiling Behaviour

India views Afghanistan as its ‘extended neighborhood.’ Indian policy makers argue that strategic presence, economic influence and foothold in country like Afghanistan would give impetus and momentum to the Indian strategic aims/objectives. The following factors provide a clear image of the vested interests of India in Afghanistan:

- India’s strategic interests in Afghanistan revolve around having a pro-Indian government in Afghanistan which can facilitate New Delhi in its regional agenda but deny Pakistan any political, strategic and economic influence in Kabul.
- Indian economic interests in Afghanistan aim to strengthen its position in the region and gain access to the mineral and energy rich Central Asian Republics (CARs). India also wants to establish a counter front against increasing economic and political influence of China in the region. Construction and development of Chabahar port in Iran was considered by New Delhi as an alternative for Gawadar to reach potential markets of CARs via Afghanistan. According to military official A (personal communication, July 19, 2021), India wants to sabotage CPEC project in Pakistan. As this mega project will not only boost Pakistan’s economy but will also lend leverage to many other states as access to Pakistan would be easy, which India does not want.
- India expanded its sphere of influence in Afghanistan to disrupt Pakistan’s security calculations vis-à-vis Kashmir. New Delhi wants to prick Islamabad because of Pakistan’s support to Kashmiri insurgents in Indian occupied Jammu and Kashmir. A pro-Indian regime in Kabul with volatile Pak-Afghan border serves this purpose well.
- *India’s involvement in Afghanistan is aimed to evoke the threat of a two-front scenario in a potential military conflict. i.e., Pincer Effect for Pakistan (Kasuri, 2016). Islamabad wants a friendly regime in Kabul to avoid being encircled by a pro-India Afghanistan to the west and New Delhi to the east.*

Spoiling Tactics Deployed by India in Afghanistan

Spoilers deploy different tactics in hybrid war to achieve their desired goals. The spoiling behaviour and tactics of New Delhi will be explored in peace negotiations in general. Indian tactics intended to delay and hinder the peace processes. Defense Minister Pervaiz Khattak (personal communication, July 12, 2021) observed:

“As India wants to destabilize Pakistan. India has been working on two options; firstly, to cancel or at least delay U.S. withdrawal, secondly, if option one is not possible, then not to let any one group to achieve power and scuttle the transition process; creating instability.”

The spoiling tactics that are being deployed by India in Afghanistan can be termed as violent or military, and non-violent or political methods.

A) Nonviolent/ Political Tactics

India’s political or non-violent measures in the long term aim to achieve Indian foreign policy goals. New Delhi has played the political tactics more sharply. Each tactic deployed by India in Afghanistan is discussed below:

i. Non-Recognition of Parties to the Conflict

After the refusal of the U.S. to seat India in Bonn Conference in 2001, New Delhi found the hidden door to Afghanistan’s internal matters through her support to Northern Alliance (Withington, 2001). India has never been the supporter of Afghan Taliban instead it always wanted anti-Taliban and pro-Indian government in Afghanistan. This act was not only directed to maximise Indian influence in Afghanistan but also enhanced its anti-Pakistan narrative and activities in Kabul. It is important to note that India due to its official policy of “no negotiation with any militant group” always refused to enter a dialogue with Afghan Taliban, as it considered that doing so would put it under pressure to start negotiations to Kashmiri insurgents as well (Basit, 2021). Pakistan, on the other hand, remained the major supporter of peace negotiations with Afghan Taliban to bring stability to Afghanistan. Zahar (2006) suggests that “the sense of insecurity which exists among the external spoilers on what would happen to them after the negotiations” motivates them to sabotage peace processes. For instance, in this case, the peace negotiation between Afghan Taliban and U.S. could undermine Indian interests, so till the dawn of Doha peace talks, India was not willing to accept Taliban even to be the major party to conflict in Afghanistan. Most Indian commentators describe that the peace deal is “entirely one-sided” and

therefore, the U.S.-withdrawal agreement has “left Afghanistan at the mercy of both the Taliban and Pakistan” (Haidar, 2020).

ii. Attempts to Stall the Peace Processes

The unstable Afghanistan would have been stable with peace long ago, had not India, its proxies and hybrid-war propagandists constructed a series of hostile machinations that showed India as a sincere and honest friend of Afghans besides negatively and falsely painting Pakistan as an opponent, foe and adversary of all Afghan ethnicities and groups including Northern Alliance and Afghan government (Hanauer, 2012). Newman and Richmond (2006) note that external actors outside the country of the conflict could spoil the conflict settlement by helping domestic spoilers and their tactics. New Delhi assisted internal spoilers for its own vested interests. In fact, this tactic was effectively deployed by India to delay the settlement of Afghan conflict. An expert commented that the Northern Alliance was against any kind of reconciliation with Afghan Taliban (Sheikh & Greenwood, 2013).

The Afghan government first led by Hamid Karzai and then by Ashraf Ghani maintained friendly relations with New Delhi. Ultimately, the real fear of India increased after the probability of Peace talks getting successful. This is so because Taliban ascent to power was considered to ultimately bring Pakistan friendly government in Kabul and Indian plans to create chaos for Pakistan on both fronts were hampered. Pakistan viewed the participation of Afghan Taliban in political configuration as a principal factor of stability. According to an analyst, from Islamabad’s perspective, “an unstable Afghanistan will affect Pakistan, not only in economic and political terms but also in security; if the Pashtuns have more participation in the Afghan power structure, then reliance on Pakistan will decrease and many problems for Pakistan will be eased” (Sheikh & Greenwood, 2013). New Delhi, on the contrary, aimed to exclude the Taliban from any peace process and thereby participation in any political setup by influencing internal spoilers.

India used its puppets in the Afghan government like Amrullah Saleh (Head of NDS, 2004-2010; and later became Vice President of Afghanistan) to derail the Peace Process. India as a spoiler would have been biggest beneficiary if the Peace Process failed (Mustafa et al., 2020). According to Pakistan’s Defence Minister (personal communication, July 12, 2021), India tried to delay the peace process by using different methods, he commented:

“India has been delaying the peace process by creating certain false ideas. India is delaying the peace process by firstly using Afghan government or other major officials to further their narrative against Pakistan and putting unrealistic demands as per condition to further peace process. Secondly, raising unnecessary alarm in neighbouring counties of Afghanistan especially CARs about likely spillover of terrorism in their region.”

iii. Building Anti-Pakistan Narrative

In Afghanistan, New Delhi was widely successful in creating anti-Pakistan narrative through media, think tanks and official discourses. This nonviolent tactic was very sharply carried out by Indian government and policy makers. The growing influence of New Delhi’s narrative was because of the involvement of Indian lobby in all the area of narrative building. An expert, S. Afridi (personal communication, July 6, 2021), analysed the construction of identity and narratives of both Pakistan and India about Afghanistan:

“The Indo-Pak narrative has nurtured, developed and evolved in a clearly defined structural mechanism in Afghanistan. The narrative of Pakistan is always considered weak as compared to Indian narrative. On international level, knowledge is produced on three levels; one through universities’ journals, next think tanks and last is the policy making. All the three tiers are Indian dominated and hence knowledge produced in Afghanistan is pro-Indian and anti-Pakistan”

India exercised control over Afghanistan electronic media as well. As the majority of people in Afghanistan are not acquainted with higher education so the firsthand opinion reaches to them through television and radio. Moreover, the Indian culture-based films and documentaries have different fan base in Afghanistan. Here, New Delhi planned to reach every home and every heart of Afghan people, to have Indian culture inculcated in their life. This media war had been played efficiently against Pakistan as India provided television satellite and radio transmitters for easy access. An Indian satellite INSAT 3-A installed as well in Afghanistan (Raza & Mustufa, 2019). The communication infrastructure of Afghanistan was also upgraded by Indian support. Besides, financial help and technical assistance were provided for reconstruction of electronic media networks. So, the concerns of Pakistan regarding Indian involvement in Afghanistan were not rootless or baseless (Javaid & Ranjha, 2016).

India’s stance is getting stronger in region and specifically in Afghanistan due to official discourse and the support of Western powers. According to I. Gul (personal communication, July 11, 2021): “India has fall mouthed Pakistan by creating a negative image in Afghanistan in addition taking advantages of Pakistan’s stakes. Even if Indian narrative may be slanted, may be skewed, may be false but still its narrative is supported by the Europeans and the West.” Undoubtedly, Western powers supported propagation of Indian narrative. Military official B (personal communication, July 11, 2021) noted:

“Indian narrative building and spoiling behaviour would have been a complete failure if the Western powers would not lend a helping hand. India is working in Afghanistan on the support provided by U.S. Even the investment, India is doing in Afghanistan, is U.S. backed.”

iv. Labelling

The Nazi propagandist, Joseph Goebbels said that speak a lie thousand times and it will become truth; the labeling implies the same. Afghanistan society itself is a victim of the labelling. Right after the 9/11 attacks, the whole Afghan society was declared as ‘the terrorists.’ The then Bonn Conference 2001 separated Government elements from the opposition elements and those who stayed in opposition were the ones labeled as the troublemakers. Following that, labelling of good and bad Taliban made the society more fragmented. Here, the international community recognized Northern alliances as the democratic government installed by the U.S. whereas the Taliban did not get any recognition. India has always been labelling Taliban as the peace spoilers and negated their role in peace talks. Pakistan on the other hand always wanted Afghan Taliban to be part of the peace negotiation in order to bring peace and stability to Afghanistan. Defence Minister of Pakistan (personal communication, July 12, 2021) commented:

“India has always spread fake news and rumors about Taliban committing atrocities against civilians with Pakistan backing. Moreover, India utilizes the diplomatic forum to spread disinformation about Taliban and that the terrorist led activities are supported by Pakistan.”

A media personal, Shahab (personnel communication, August 12, 2021) pointed out that “Propaganda is taking over the Afghan peace process.” New Delhi has long accused Islamabad of providing support to *Afghan Taliban*. The former Ambassador to Afghanistan, Rustam Shah Mohmand (personal communication, August 12, 2021) noted:

“Pakistan has always been behind the idea to include Afghan Taliban in the political structure of government. Now any wrong done on part of Taliban is considered to be backed by Pakistan. Taliban being one of the party in creating chaos in Afghan society are directly associated to Pakistan, so Pakistan will definitely have to bear the consequences which may even come from our neighboring state India.”

v. Financing Afghan Society against Pakistan

The people of Afghanistan have little knowledge and are less acquainted with the comforts of daily life. Majority People in Afghanistan still live on mountains and are working to earn daily bread for life. In such situation if few of them are funded with money and luxuries in order to act against Pakistan they do it happily. Exploiting this situation, India planted feeling of love and harmony for India and rivalry for Pakistan. Military official A (personal communication, July 19, 2021) highlighted the role of Indian Embassy and India’s intelligence agency, Research & Analysis Wing (RAW) in financing Afghan society:

“India has been doing in Afghanistan what it did in Bangladesh. Indian Embassy funds the locals and the activities are conducted through intelligence agencies. One of the India Professors in his lecture said that we just need to invest money; we don’t need to invest forces in Afghanistan against Pakistan. The reason is that Afghan people are less literate and poorer, so are easy utilized to carry out India’s interests.”

He further noted: “even if Afghan are caught [in Pakistan] and accept to be Indian spy their statements are of no use. And India cannot be blamed for using Afghan national as a spy.”

Rustam Shah Mohmand argued that many Afghan are of the view that Pakistan is spoiler as it supported the war against terrorism in Afghanistan with the spoiler United States (Personnel Communication, August 12, 2021). However, Pakistan wanted political solution to Afghan conflict in a fair manner. Newman & Richmond (2006) also note that party considered as spoiler may not be seeking to spoil the peace process, but rather to improve it and make it fairer.

A regional expert and Professor, B. Shah (personal communication, August 8, 2021) also captured this Indian tactic to turn members of Afghan society against Pakistan by describing that:

“Pakistan has done a lot for Afghanistan but failed badly in building a positive image. India, on the other hand, invested in infrastructure and communication for facilitation of local Afghans like gifting public buses with the notion of Indo-Afghan friendship and it was realized and appreciated by Afghani people. India invested in Afghanistan but has cashed its investment in shape of achieving anti Pakistan narrative.”

vi. Exploiting the Ethnic and Religious Differences

The ethnic profile of Afghanistan shows the amalgamation of Tajiks, Hazaras, Uzbeks and Pashtun. Religiously, Sunni and Shiite sect are more dominant than other sects. Afghanistan today is divided among these ethnic and sectarian groups. India used these ethnic and religious differences to promote its desired interests. Military official B (Personal communication, August 9, 2021) noted that India spent “huge amount of money to increase the anti-Pakistan sentiments” in “those provinces where the minority groups are dominant” so that “people act against Pakistan.” Moreover, the sectarian issue in both the countries “is also being used by India, as the Shiite

sect in Afghanistan is being used to sabotage peace, the Shiites in Pakistan due to religious inclination takes side of Afghan Shiites.”

The divergence in religious and cultural norms makes the society more diverse. However, India targets these differences and utilizes it against Pakistan. According to S. Afridi (personal communication, July 6, 2021):

“The target audience in Afghanistan to be directed for spoiling purposes are two broader sections; first pro-India and anti-Pakistan and second pro-Pakistan which are anti-India. Pro-Indian are nationalist, powerful, the supporters of Pashtunistan and anti-Pakistan, non-ethnic Pashtuns. They have money and access to knowledge corridor, largest representatives in universities, hand in policy making and linkages with many international forums even with United Nations. Pro-Pakistan is anti-nationalist, anti-communist, anti-monarchist and anti-socialist and they have guns in their hands, with less knowledge and low income.”

Pakistan extended support to these anticommunist and anti-monarchist, which makes Pakistan the trouble creator in eyes of international community whereas the original spoiler who sought to sabotage the peace processes in Afghanistan only in order to get its regional interest secured is India.

vii. Soft Power as a Spoiling Tactic

One of the major tactics that India applied to attain its interest in the region through Afghanistan is the application of soft power in Afghanistan. India utilized its economy to play a role in Kabul affairs. Ranging from industrial assistance to agricultural upgradation, India helped Afghan government to build up security measures and communicational lines. Funds in name of development projects were being provided on large scale. This was the clear projection of India playing the soft power card in Afghanistan (Raza & Mustafa, 2019).

The strategy of soft power was more intended to grasp the attention of local Afghan nationals. Various agreements and protocol had been signed among Afghan government and India for the training and education of officials of state-owned institutions. In 2008, Afghan local government officers were trained by Indian officials under an agreement ‘Memorandum of Understanding on Cooperation of Local Governance.’ Perhaps the funding and assistance provided by India to Afghanistan was mostly state owned and the state-to-state collaboration marked a significant cooperation. It is important to note that the private sector has not shown any interest or involvement (Wang, 2018). New Delhi invested in Afghanistan with the aim to forward its regional interests, (S. Afridi, personal communication, July 6, 2021) noted:

“Indian strategy is extension of smart power. The leverage of smart power extends about 3 billion dollars, exchange of students and medical facilitation, being fifth largest donor, and random visits of Karzai and Ashraf Ghani to India. Using this strategy, Indians want to secure their objectives but many scholars consider this to be a failure.”

It is important to note that India used the Afghan soil against Pakistan in collusion with Afghan government (I. Gul, personal communication, July 11, 2021):

“Because it is much easier to invest in Afghan government, the Afghan security forces and at the same time they also invest on proxy terrorist groups. New Delhi provides funding and all sort of support to Afghan Government, so that they remain indebted to India and hence keeps paddling the Indian narrative in different forums as far as Pakistan is concerned.”

In fact, India has been manipulating the situation in Afghanistan since the late 20th century. Within the state, the disturbance is exaggerated to make the environment more favourable for India. New Delhi’s use of the troubled situation in Afghanistan in its favour by Investing money for the reconstruction purposes was not aimed at its development but to “carry out India’s vested interests in the region which can be accomplished through Afghanistan widely” (Personnel Communication with B. Shah, August 8, 2021).

India has contributed nearly 3 billion dollars for developmental projects and is the ‘largest regional donor’ in Afghanistan. An Indian Scholar, Rani D. Mullen (2017) discussed the way India had been helping or donating the war-torn state or conflict-ridden states in order to achieve the foreign policy goals. Mullen points out that this non-conventional aid programme generated vast and quick profit for India. As the conflict affected states like Afghanistan are willing to provide any help to India after the delivery of development aid.

B. Violent/ Military Tactics

Violent or military tactics are those actions that cause destruction, pain or suffering. These tactics are unjust and violation of law. India was involved in different violent tactics like bombings, widespread terror, facilitating the internal spoilers and others. Each of these is discussed below:

i. Sabotage Peace Processes by Supporting Terrorist Organizations

India has been involved in planning and supporting, financing terrorist organizations to carry out different suicidal attacks whether in Afghanistan or in Pakistan to make the peace deals fail. Hazrat (2018) notes that India is carrying out covert operations of ethnic violence, creating militancy, committing suicidal attacks, exploding bombs, target killings and sectarian strife. The same idea was given by a prominent journalist, I. Gul (personal communication, July 11, 2021) in these words:

“India uses the proxy terror groups to infuse disturbance in Pakistan. India basically employs certain people or groups to carry out subversive activities like spending 50-100 million dollars an year on proxy

terrorists like Tehrik-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) and Islamic State-Khurasan (IS-K) province to keep Pakistan on tetra hooks.”

According to a former military official:

“India remained involved in Afghanistan to infuse terror in Pakistan and the biggest evidence is in the shape of captured KulbhushanJadhev. India also funded the anti-Pakistan sections in shape of arms and ammunitions. Whenever a terrorist attack or bombing is carried out in Pakistan, the weapons used turn out to be Indian manufactured.”

New Delhi sees U.S.-Taliban agreement from its own strategic prism. In fact, New Delhi favoured not to deal with Taliban over a deal that favoured Pakistan (Ahmad, 2020).

Pakistan has concerns over the Indian involvement in Afghanistan with a main motive to destabilize Pakistan. In September 2020, Pakistan Army and Government issued a common brochure regarding Indian involvement in Afghanistan. It detailed the tactics, India deployed in Afghanistan to sabotage the peace of region and ongoing peace negotiations. The then Foreign Minister, Shah Mehmood Qureshi said, “Bank transactions, letters, communication intercepts show India’s terror financing, arms supply, training to and harboring of militants” (Syed, 2020).

Pakistan has blamed India for supporting and funding terrorists for creating destabilization in the region with complete evidence against India. In the same press conference, Prime Minister of Pakistan, Imran Khan said:

“Pakistan has provided undeniable evidence of state sponsored terrorism of India inside Pakistan. Direct involvement of Indian state and their financial and military support for terrorism have been given to the world”

Major General Babar also gave specific details about terror financing by RAW in Afghanistan against Pakistan. He provided details of two transactions made through Indian Banks; an amount of \$28,000 was transferred by Punjab Bank India, and another transaction of \$55,851 was made by an Indian national named Mr. Manmeet from Indian Bank, New Delhi. Both transactions were received at Afghanistan International Bank. While showing letters in Dari, the military spokesperson said India paid Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) leadership a huge amount of \$820,000 through its collaborators. The spokesperson for Pakistan military also provided details of the supply of arms, weapons and ammunition by Indian authorities in Afghanistan for creating instability in Pakistan. He said that 87 terrorists’ camps were operated under Indian intelligence agencies to target Pakistan. Out of 87 camps, 66 were located in Afghanistan, whereas the others 21 were operating and functioning from India (Syed, 2020).

ii. Support to Internal Spoilers for Continued Strife in Afghanistan

To support the Indian narrative in Afghanistan and make the anti-Pakistan dilemma stronger, India funded the internal spoilers at large. Whether it was in shape of development aid or humanitarian aid, the main motive behind this money was funding the internal spoilers of the peace process, creating instability in Afghanistan vis-a-vis disturbing Pakistan. Defence Minister of Pakistan on this remarked, that one of the tactic that New Delhi used in Afghanistan was “to derail the peace process is material and financial support to anti-Taliban groups to spread infighting. This internal disturbance caused delay in peace negotiations”(personal communication, July 12, 2021)

Terrorist groups like Islamic State-Khurasan province (IS-K) and TTP were backed by New Delhi. Afghan National Army (ANA) and NDS were also funded luxuriously. India pumped in approximately 3 billion dollars into Afghanistan in the last fifteen years in the form of so-called aid for social development, almost one-third of it was for fueling the war machine. In terms of training 7200 Afghan personnel including interpreters were trained from 2006-2020 (Naureen, & Waqar, 2020).

iii. Use of Indian Embassy/ Consulates for Clandestine Operations

Approximately 3,000-4,000 Indian nationals had been working on different ongoing projects across Afghanistan till the ascendancy of Afghan Taliban to power in August 2021. India also pursued the strategy to set up consulates in Kandahar, Nangarhar, Herat and Mazar-e-Sharif. These consulates were of concern to Islamabad as Pakistan believed that New Delhi supported TTP and Baloch *insurgency* inside Pakistan through these consulates. In July 2006 Senator Mushahid Hussain pointed out that the Indian Embassy in Kabul and its consulates in Kandahar and Jalalabad are conducting “clandestine activities inside Pakistan.” In July 2009 meeting at the in Sharm el-Sheik, Pakistani Prime Minister Yousaf Reza Gilani presented a dossier to Indian Prime Minister Manmohan Singh containing evidence of Brahmadagh Bugti meeting Indian operatives and officials in Kabul. The dossier also revealed Indian consulate at Kandahar was controlling and funding the Baloch insurgents (Syed, 2009). In August 2016, a blast in Quetta, Balochistan killed at least 95 people. Pakistan considered “the [attack an attempt to sabotage CPEC](#)” and [Chief Minister of Balochistan accused New Delhi](#) of being behind the attack using Afghan soil (Shahid, 2016). Undoubtedly, Indian strategic interests in Afghanistan were driven by her self-interest and not by the stability of Afghanistan as shown to the world. In fact, geo-political and geo strategic location of Afghanistan is an important factor for India to use a pro-Indian government to destabilise Pakistan (Kiran, 2009). Former U.S. Special Envoy to Afghanistan and Pakistan stated: “Pakistan’s concerns over Indian consulates involvement in anti-Pakistan and terrorist activities are

based on realities and facts” (Armitage et al., 2010). Similarly, American scholar, Fair (2014) remarked, “India is airing unrest and militancy in Afghanistan.”

iv. **The RAW-NDS Nexus to Sabotage Peace Processes**

The intelligence agencies of both the states are in collaboration with one another i.e., Indian premier Intelligence Agency (RAW) and Afghan National Directorate of Security (NDS). The RAW-NDS nexus worked together to make the regional cooperation strong and making Indian objectives easier to achieve. Various RAW personnel remain loyal friend to agents of NDS. Mutual training and operations were carried out frequently (Raza & Mustufa, 2019). The most worrying thing was penetration of RAW into Afghan military intelligence. This NDS-RAW nexus did not give space for the collaboration between the Intelligence Agency of Pakistan (ISI) and NDS. Indian military academies trained Afghan Army officers and soldiers and anti-Pakistan ideas were being inculcated in the minds and souls of these soldiers from the day one of their training. NDS officers were trained and provided with weapons from the Indian Intelligence Academies. The bureaucrats and Civil Servants of Afghanistan were being trained in Indian Civil Services Academies and grant in the form of millions of dollars was also provided by the Indian government for the capacity making of the Afghan bureaucracy. After establishing its strong intelligence network in Afghanistan, Indian consulates in Afghanistan were reportedly found in anti-Pakistan activities. The NDS-RAW nexus was also promoting, supporting and backing IS-K in Afghanistan in order to defeat Afghan Taliban. It could be argued that IS-K in Afghanistan aims to make Afghanistan a breeding ground for conflagration, extremism and violence and the people of Afghanistan suffered from this unholy nexus (“India-Afghanistan,” 2016).

Implications for Pakistan

India in Afghanistan has undoubtedly played the role of spoiler by employing different tactics to carry out its interests in the region specifically against Pakistan. India deployed spoiling tactics sharply to delay and hinder peace process in Afghanistan. Indian presence on Afghan land remained a cause of concern for Pakistan as India’s designs were not to aid Afghanistan but to destabilize Pakistan through its northwestern neighbour. The above discussion drafts following implications for Pakistan:

- India, trying to maintain its regional status tried to malign Pakistan particularly its tribal areas as ‘safe haven’ for terrorists. India desires to penalize Pakistan via segregating and expelling it from regional scene. To this end, India’s so-called aid of developing Afghanistan worked against Pakistan (Javaid, 2016).
- India instigated problems and insurgency in Balochistan with the objective of detaching it from Pakistan in order to limit economic and strategic potentiality of Pakistan. Islamabad blamed New Delhi’s consulates in Jalalabad, Kandahar, Herat and Mazar-i-Sharif for inciting issues and insurgencies in two provinces of Pakistan, viz. Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Indian consulates on Afghan soil worked together with terrorist groups to stir insurgency in Pakistan providing armaments as well as financing Baloch Nationalist Movement in Balochistan and TTP (Jaffery, 2020).
- To attain political objectives against Pakistan, India supported its proxy, Northern alliance. New Delhi used Islamabad’s support as a leverage against Pakistan.
- India tried to lessen strategic significance of Gwadar port for Kabul and CARs by developing road links to Iran’s Chahbahar port (Kiran, 2009) and fomenting terrorism in Balochistan.
- New Delhi investment for the local Afghan society and its propaganda created a negative image of Islamabad among Afghans.

Conclusion

Following the attacks of 9/11, peace processes in Kabul were derailed several times as hybrid conflict gave birth to internal as well external spoilers and their main target behind this spoiling attitude was to achieve their vested interests. India has the crown of being major spoiler in this regard and deployed military and political tactics to sabotage peace processes. Being one of the emerging economic powers, India cashed its position in the region through post-9/11 Afghanistan. Regional states were more interested in achieving peace in Afghanistan. Russia, China, Central Asian Republics, Iran and Pakistan all were on board. The only state to remain indifferent and opposed to peace negotiations was India with serious implications for Afghan conflict settlement as well as for security of Pakistan. Following American withdrawal on August 30, 2021, Taliban took control of Afghanistan. Taliban are pursuing a consensus with neighbouring countries to stabilize Afghanistan and thereby bringing peace and stability to the region. It appears that there is no role for India’s spoiling tactics ahead in Afghanistan.

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